

Outcomes of the First Overall Architecture Workshop

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1 Summary

The path towards an overall architecture for the National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) is a participatory process: integrating the distributed and grass-roots tailored setups of the 26 NFDI consortia into a federated and interoperable ecosystem. To address this, the NFDI Working Group Overall Architecture (WG OA)¹ of the *NFDI Section Common Infrastructures (Section Infra)* has initiated a series of workshops. The first was held on November 26–27, 2025, at the GWDG in Göttingen and a second one is planned on April 14–15, 2026 at the RWTH Aachen. This document recapitulates the results of the first expert forum with contributions from the 16 NFDI consortia that attended (out of 26), as well as from 5 basic services of Base4NFDI. The representatives present in the workshop collectively shaped and agreed on a layered reference architecture defining common technical building blocks, including identity and access management, storage services, and compute infrastructures. This approach creates an agreed understanding, decoupling infrastructure provision from scientific applications and supporting both academic and commercial infrastructure providers.

2 Organic Convergence of Architectural Models

The NFDI Working Group Overall Architecture (WG OA)² is part of the *NFDI Section Common Infrastructures (Section Infra)*. The aim of this group is not to impose a rigid, top-down enterprise architecture that ignores the specificities of the various NFDI research domains. Rather, its objective is to develop a strategic shared vision and define a technical architecture for a federated research data and service infrastructure that supports diverse scientific communities through a collaborative, consensus-driven process.

A central topic dominating the discourse at the first workshop was the definition of the **scope of the overall architecture** and the extent to which "architecture" encompasses organizational and governance structures versus purely technical stacks. To remain effective and agile, a decision of the workshop was to focus the WG OA on the technical considerations. Consequently, business-related aspects like legal frameworks, financing models, and high-level governance will be delegated to joint working groups led by other NFDI bodies, such as the *Section ELSA (Ethical, Legal, and Social Aspects)*³, the *Task Force Governance & Sustainability*⁴, and Base4NFDI⁵ and will be integrated once a consensus is reached. This strategic limitation of the scope of the NFDI architecture allows the experts to focus on tangible deliverables: interoperability of platforms, infrastructure and operations scope definitions, and a federated cloud-service-based reference model for an overall architecture.

A presentation and **evaluation of the technical architectures of the consortia** at the first workshop further revealed that they are more aligned in their visions than previously anticipated. By identifying

¹Politze, M., Wieder, P., Schimmler, S., & Diepenbroek, M. (2025, April). Concept for setting up the overall architecture working group in the nfdi section "common infrastructures". <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15210894>

²Politze, M., Wieder, P., Schimmler, S., & Diepenbroek, M. (2025, April). Concept for setting up the overall architecture working group in the nfdi section "common infrastructures". <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15210894>

³Boehm, F., Buchner, B., Kipker, D.-K., Kuntz, A., Petri, G., Sax, U., Schaar, K., von Suchodoletz, D., & Vettermann, O. (2021, November). Sektionskonzept "ethical, legal & social aspects" (section-elsa). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5675972>

⁴Ferenz, S., Miller, B., Busse, C., Demandt, É., Eberl, F., Ebert, B., Fluck, J., Förstner, K. U., Goedicke, M., Hennig, C., Jagusch, G. W., Jansen, L., Keller, C., Krieger, U., Rettberg, N., Schrade, T., Seegert, J., von Suchodoletz, D., Trippel, T., & Weidtkamp-Peters, S. (2025, April). Arbeitsplan 2025 der taskforce governance and sustainability (tfgs) - schritte zur weiterentwicklung unserer nfdi. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15181340>

⁵<https://base4nfdi.de>

these organic convergences, the WG OA aims to construct a **blueprint** that reflects the reality of the solutions used within the NFDI consortia. In the future, the agreed architectural approach will provide the NFDI with a common starting point for discussing other aspects of the architecture such as data flows, data storage, data and service interoperability, governance and service management.

3 Layered Service Model

As a first approximation, the WG OA proposed a blueprint of interactions between the different stakeholder groups in relation to offerings, as they are commonly modelled by commercial IT infrastructures, namely Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS), Platform as a Service (PaaS), and Software as a Service (SaaS)⁶ (Figure 1). In this model, the end-user (the researcher) does not interact directly with the technical solution provider (e.g., storage). Instead, the researcher interacts with the consortium's service ("business to customer", B2C), which in turn utilizes the resources provided by a technical solution provider on a business to business (B2B) relationship. Even though the terms are borrowed from enterprise lingo, in this case "Business" refers to research organisations, consortiums, platforms, or infrastructures offering a service. Similarly, "Customer" refers to individual researchers, groups, collaborations, and research organisations using a service - in alignment with the mission of NFDI to target academic organisations, their employees and individual researchers.

Figure 1: A **hand-over model** illustrates the different roles of NFDI, NFDI consortia and providers to successfully offer research data management services. This gradually hides technical operation and hardware complexity and allows scalability of services to a wider user base and specific scientific processes and applications.

There will certainly be situations in which individuals need to use technical solutions directly. However, domain-specific services will account for the majority of usage (direct interaction). Hence, clarifying the role of the NFDI as a legal entity (e.V.) and its consortia as a mediator between users and technical solution providers is not only aligned with the funding programme but is also a crucial prerequisite for deriving an overall architecture. This defines the expectation that NFDI consortia are supplied with ready-to-use operational environments in which their services can be deployed and operated, reducing the complexity for provisioning and maintaining technical environments themselves.

Mapping this conceptual hand-over model onto the established cloud computing service model translates the concept into a practical and widely understood framework. While NFDI consortia

⁶Mell, P. M., & Grance, T. (2011). *The nist definition of cloud computing*. <https://doi.org/10.6028/nist.sp.800-145>

primarily provide services (SaaS), some also offer platforms (PaaS) as part of their mission. Hence, the hand-over points do not fully align with the cloud service model and may vary depending on the service under consideration. In any case, the model serves as a means for communication and documentation of responsibilities.

IaaS and PaaS offers are not complimentary, their provision and allocation must be appropriately funded, brokered, managed, and facilitated. This may be achieved through agreements with university computing centres, other research infrastructure providers or commercial offerings (all cases are consequently subsumed as “providers”). The key goal is to increase and maximize the value derived from existing infrastructure funding and provide non-discriminatory access. An allocation process should be comparable in simplicity to established models such as commercial cloud provisioning, institutional resource access via internal approval processes, or HPC usage procedures.

This decoupling of responsibilities of NFDI (and its consortia) and providers serves two strategic purposes:

Complexity hiding: Researchers/users and NFDI consortia are shielded from the technical complexities of service management. Providers are shielded from discipline-specific requirements of NFDI consortia and researchers/users.

Scalability: A single (compute and storage) provider can serve multiple consortia through a unified B2B interface, and a single consortium gains flexibility to aggregate offers from multiple (compute and storage) providers to increase performance or resilience.

The primary technical outcome of the workshop is the preliminary validation of a layered reference architecture for the NFDI. This model acts as a “map” for placing services and clarifying responsibilities (Figure 2).

Figure 2: The **layered architecture map** subdivides the cloud service model into functional components. Responsibilities for these building blocks are assigned or shared between the providers, NFDI and NFDI consortia. Even though layers are depicted impermeable, services will likely only use a subset of the lower layers.

3.1 The Infrastructure Layer (IaaS)

At the foundation of the NFDI architecture lies the physical infrastructure – compute and storage connected in a network.

Function: This layer abstracts raw hardware capacities for compute and storage from the physical to a software defined infrastructure

Managed by: Infrastructure providers (e.g., university computing centers, NHR centres, core facilities, national research centres, and commercial offerings).

Strategic Implication: NFDI as a legal entity (e.V.) acts as a federator and broker. NFDI negotiates the requirements (SLAs, capacity) and terms of access to these resources on behalf of the NFDI consortia (service providers) and their discipline-specific users. The architecture implies this B2B relationship where infrastructure providers deliver technical solutions (raw capacity) via standardized and interoperable protocols (e.g., S3, WebDAV for storage; SLURM, OpenStack for compute) to services coordinated by NFDI consortia defining the functional requirements.

3.1.1 Building Blocks of the IaaS Layer

The basic infrastructure comprises the required compute and storage resources. Ideally, the hosting environment for virtual machines or containers supports automation, for example to enable automatic service redeployment in the event of failures or during updates. Compute and storage resources should be located in close proximity to each other in terms of network connectivity and available bandwidth. The optimal configuration depends on the specific workflows, data volumes, and access patterns of individual services and research use cases.

General purpose **compute** services usually require virtual machines (e.g., OpenStack) or containerized environments (e.g., Docker, Kubernetes). In addition, many scientific workflows rely on high-performance and high-throughput computing resources (HPC, HTC) utilized by batch jobs (e.g., SLURM). These environments typically require specialized, directly attached parallel storage systems that provide high I/O performance. Such storage is usually intended for temporary, scratch-like usage and is not designed for long-term, reliable data storage.

Dedicated **storage** resources are used both for maintaining service configurations and for storing user data. Depending on the locally provided infrastructure, storage may be delivered via traditional file systems (e.g., NFS) or through object storage solutions (e.g., S3). The storage system must provide the appropriate level of redundancy to ensure data integrity and long-term availability in accordance with service requirements.

3.2 The Platform Layer (PaaS)

Above the hardware sits the platform layer, which provides runtime environments and middleware necessary to deploy discipline-oriented applications.

Function: This layer includes container orchestration (Kubernetes), database hosting, and workflow management systems. It bundles available resources in the federation and promotes access through federated IAM.

Managed by: Platform providers or NFDI consortia, governed by NFDI.

Strategic Implication: By standardizing the PaaS layer (e.g., agreeing on a standard Container-as-a-Service API), the NFDI can enable the portability of services between different infrastructure providers.

3.2.1 Building Blocks of the PaaS Layer

The technical sharing of capacities requires the set-up of practical **resource federations** - sociotechnical frameworks in which these capacities are offered and can be consumed (e.g., multi-cloud, marketplace, Jupyter4NFDI). This layer requires federated identity management and accounting to make services from the infrastructure layer widely accessible by service operators from the NFDI consortia and expose the technical interfaces in a unified manner. Ideally, the process to access the resources in the federation should be comparable in simplicity to established models such as commercial cloud provisioning, institutional resource access via internal approval processes, or standard HPC usage procedures. Numerous domain-specific services are built on a comparatively small and converging set of platform and infrastructure technologies (e.g., Web technologies, containers, Linux). This convergence at the lower layers provides the opportunity to define a coherent platform offer.

Further abstraction and complexity hiding requires higher level **middleware APIs** that work on top of the federated resources. These can be oriented towards further automation and orchestration of the infrastructure layer (e.g., Kubernetes APIs, Infrastructure as Code/Terraform) or offer managed hosting of backend applications (e.g., SQL databases, triple stores, serverless workflows, PID services) that can in turn be used by application developers to build software services.

3.3 The Service Layer (SaaS)

The top layer consists of the domain-specific applications used by researchers – like electronic lab notebooks, image repositories, or text analysis tools.

Function: This layer is rightfully heterogeneous. The architecture does not seek to standardize the functionality of these tools and services but rather their interfaces, data formats and quality standards; primarily where necessary for the scientific use cases.

Managed by: NFDI consortia and basic services.

Strategic Implication: Depending on the scientific discipline, a diverse set of applications can interact with one another. Where it is useful for the scientific discipline, this layer needs to ensure data interoperability by standardized data representations (e.g. FDO) or shared and unified identities through IAM4NFDI.

3.3.1 Building Blocks of the SaaS Layer

To operate the bridge from the technical infrastructure to the specific use cases, a software development and deployment (DevOps) environment is required. Infrastructure for maintaining **source code and software packages** (e.g., GitLab, Forgejo, package and container registries) are used for distribution of software and for continuous integration.

Protocols and concepts for **data access** (e.g., content addressing, PIDs, IPFS, FAIR Digital Objects) define how datasets and objects are located, retrieved, and verified independently of the physical location of the data. Combined with federated access management, this ensures reproducible, secure,

and machine-actionable access in an AI-ready data ecosystem that is fully aligned with current legislation, including strict compliance with sensitive data regulations.

A shared meaning for data through standardized meta data, alongside controlled vocabularies, taxonomies, and ontologies, enables interoperability and automated reasoning. **Semantics** services (e.g., TS4NFDI, OLS, OntoPortal, AIMS) host, version, and resolve terms and relationships. By centralizing semantic resources and offering APIs for term resolution and validation, these services reduce ambiguity and make cross-dataset integration and FAIR compliance tractable for downstream applications.

Data repositories (e.g., Invenio, Dataverse) and **registries** aim for data publication according to the FAIR principles. While there are typically discipline-specific instances, the operation of these repositories is widely agnostic; especially repositories and registries profit from broad standardization of interfaces for data exchange (e.g., OAI-PMH, DataCite, DCat).

Community-specific or endorsed **data and processing services** (e.g., GitLab, Omero, Galaxy, Jupyter, REANA, CloWM, DataHub, Coscine, OneStop4All) are targeting a user base of researchers within the scientific disciplines. These services must cater to the specific needs of their user base, so standardization is challenging and must be driven by scientific use cases. These efforts greatly profit from the standardization in the lower layers of the architecture.

4 Thematic Deep Dives

The workshop facilitated thematic deep dives to connect the overall architectural vision with recent activities, fill gaps in the discussion and implementation or consider other general topics of interest. While the results of these deep dives have a high relevance to make sure the architecture fits to the needs of the NFDI, they will be strategically placed in other (existing) working groups of *Section Infra*, other sections, or task forces.

4.1 Common Building Blocks

There is a strong desire for an academic cloud infrastructure, comparable to commercial providers regarding ease-of-use, but which also respects data privacy and cost constraints to strengthen digital sovereignty. Building a comprehensive “NFDI Cloud” or “NFDI Multi-Cloud” is a massive undertaking. The pathway of the so-far unsuccessful Multi-Cloud basic service proposal highlights the scepticism regarding a purely project-based approach to such critical infrastructure. The proposed layered architecture offers a potential solution to the challenge of connecting infrastructure providers in a federation, especially regarding the currently selected service providers in the context of the NFDI-Storage call. The successful participants of the NFDI-Storage call⁷ and other existing infrastructure providers involved in NFDI consortia should be included in this discussion in the future.

Further discussions are seen at the current core of the WG OA and are continuing its framework.

⁷“With its ‘NFDI Storage 2025’ initiative, the DFG is providing around €20 million in funding for storage systems at German universities. This concerted action addresses the NFDI consortias’ increased need for independent infrastructure for data provision, long-term archiving and data processing.” Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft. (2025, January 21). Datenspeichersysteme zur Stärkung der NFDI [Data storage systems to strengthen the NFDI]. <https://www.dfg.de/de/aktuelles/neuigkeiten-themen/info-wissenschaft/2025/ifw-25-43>

4.2 Data Flow and Sovereignty

A traditional model of a centralized "Data Lake" for the NFDI was largely rejected in favor of a "Data Mesh" architecture⁸. In a Data Mesh, data is treated as a product, and ownership remains with the domain-oriented teams (the scientists) who understand it best. The "Overall Architecture" does not centralise the data itself, but rather the governance and standards that enable data sharing. Among other approaches FAIR Digital Objects (FDOs) can act as an enabling technology. FDOs are a unit composed of data and metadata regulated by structures or schemas, and with an assigned globally unique and persistent identifier (PID), making the data self-describing and machine-actionable⁹.

Future discussions should be integrated by the *WG Persistent Identifiers (WG PID)* and *WG Data Integration (WG DI)* in the *Section Infra*. The WG OA aims to pick up the topic once it is further matured in the other WGs.

4.3 Data Interoperability and Standardization

Comparable to overall data flow, data interoperability is another technical requirement to allow effective data exchange of datasets within and between NFDI consortia. In this context, interoperability was discussed in terms of both syntactic and semantic aspects. A substantial part of the discussion focused on reviewing and comparing file formats, metadata models, and semantic frameworks already documented by the participating consortia, with the aim of obtaining an overview of existing practices rather than proposing new ones. It became evident that, for comparable tasks, certain file formats are already shared across multiple consortia.

Specific file formats may serve as crystallization points (e.g. RO-Crate, Zarr); however, their adoption will be highly dependent on the nature of datasets. Semantic interoperability is already well-supported technologically by the linked data framework and several top- and mid-level ontologies (e.g. Schema.org, NFDIcore¹⁰) that require appropriate alignment. To create the necessary visibility, it is essential to use the NFDI sections to officially promote established approaches as formal recommendations.

Future discussions will be conducted in the *Section (Meta)data, Terminologies and Provenance* and the reconstituted *WG DI* in the *Section Infra*. WG OA aims to pick up the topic once it is further matured in the other WGs.

4.4 Standards and Documentation

A recurring discussion point is the ambiguity of the term "service". At least for technical services that can be located in the layered architecture, a set of guidelines is required for the operation and evaluation of the services within the federated offering. Among potential others, the deep dive discussed that from the viewpoint of the layered architecture these guidelines should include

- federated AAI (IAM4NFDI),
- REST / openAPI based interfaces,
- established metadata standards, and

⁸Dehghani, Z. (2019). How to move beyond a monolithic data lake to a distributed data mesh. <https://martinowler.com/articles/data-monolith-to-mesh.html>

⁹FDOs furthermore require implementations such as RO-crate (<https://www.researchobject.org/>) or FAIR Data Point (<https://www.fairdatapoint.org/>) that adequately match the considered domain and use cases.

¹⁰<https://github.com/ISE-FIZKarlsruhe/nfdicore>

- modeling of knowledge in Knowledge Graphs (KGI4NFDI)

Quality assessments like the technology readiness level (TRL) are a sensible start for a minimum requirement for all services, for infrastructure providers more formal assessments are likely required (e.g. BSI, ISO 27001).

Discussion on this topic should be continued in the *Task Force Governance & Sustainability* and is currently considered out of scope for WG OA.

4.5 Service Portfolio and EOSC Alignment

As the German National Node in the EOSC Federation, the NFDI must ensure its portfolio is technically compatible with EOSC standards. This means NFDI services must support the EOSC AAI (Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure) and publish metadata in the EOSC Profile format. It further needs to provide some foundational components, such as a resource and a service registry. The WG OA serves as the bridge, translating European requirements into technical specifications for the German consortia.

Due to the bottom-up nature of service development, a distinction between “service registry” (a list of all available services) and a “service portfolio” (a curated list of mature and sustainable products) may be required.

Future discussions on EOSC alignment — especially architecture alignment — will be continued in the WG OA. Agreements with regards to an NFDI “Service Portfolio” should be pursued in the *Task Force Governance & Sustainability* and is currently considered out of scope for WG OA. Further discussions with regards to a German EOSC Node will be continued in the newly established *Section International Engagement*.

5 Alignment and Integration

This first shared architectural vision is not theoretical; it is already being implemented through the services of the NFDI consortia and it is supported by the Basic Services.

5.1 Architectural Integration of Basic Services

The reference architecture relies on the existence of shared components that no single consortium has to build alone. The workshop discussed the role within the overall architecture of several base services:

IAM4NFDI: Provides the foundational identity layer

Accounting4NFDI: Provides means for rationing and resource sharing

PID4NFDI: Provides the persistent identifiers necessary for overarching data flows

Jupyter4NFDI: Bundles compute resources to make them accessible across consortia

KGI4NFDI: Builds the foundation for aggregating data across consortia

Obviously the role of the other base services needs to be evaluated in the context of the overall architecture in the future.

5.2 International Alignment: The European Context

The NFDI architecture evolves within the context of a rapidly evolving European landscape. The workshop explicitly aligned the NFDI's technical trajectory with major European initiatives.

The workshop emphasizes that the role as *German National Node* within the EOSC Federation is not just a political designation but a technical one. The overall architecture must implement the *EOSC Interoperability Framework*¹¹ to ensure that German researchers can seamlessly access European resources and vice versa. The workshop identified specific touchpoints, such as the need for a "hybrid cloud" connector that allows NFDI services to burst into EOSC compute resources and vice versa.

Beyond EOSC, the various emerging European Data Spaces (e.g., European Health Data Space (EHDS), Catena-X) are becoming reference frameworks for cross-border data sharing and interoperability along economic sectors. To remain relevant in the long term, the NFDI architecture must therefore ensure compatibility with these initiatives, aligning technical standards and governance models so that NFDI services can integrate seamlessly into evolving European data ecosystems.

6 Conclusion and Roadmap

The NFDI overall architecture is being built to support and facilitate, not constrain, the goals of the discipline-specific NFDI consortia. The organic growth approach ensures that domain-specific requirements are the primary driver of architectural decisions. NFDI consortia are further encouraged to support their technical staff in participating in the WG OA activities, as this is the forum where the standards affecting their future operations are being set.

With the first workshop of the WG OA begins the transition to a consolidated, federated technical infrastructure for the NFDI. By securing a consensus and minimal agreement on a **blueprint architecture** and the **common building blocks**, the WG OA has successfully taken this first step. However, transitioning from existing operational setups to this model will be a long-term effort, and it is also acceptable if some services are unable to adopt it (e.g., due to external dependencies, sensitive data, distributed/federated services).

The second workshop will take place April 14–15, 2026 at the RWTH Aachen, and aims to further detail the architectural framework proposed. However, its success depends on the continued active engagement of the NFDI consortia. Along with the self-understanding of the WG OA of integrating the grass-roots setups, the NFDI consortia have to adopt these recommendations to facilitate interoperability and establish sustainable resource provision with providers governed by the NFDI.

¹¹Orazio, S. D., Eva, S., Jean-Karim, H., Mark, V. D. S., Wierenga, K., Paolo, M., Damian, T., Norberto, M. J., Álvaro, L. G., Wim, H., Jerome, P., & Lene, K. A. (2023, October). A landscape overview of the eosoc interoperability framework - capabilities and gaps. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8399710>

